

OUTLOOK

Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

Quantum information technologies
for 6G and beyond

May 2025 No 35

10.5281/zenodo.15694687

WWRF Working Group 6G

WWRF Outlook 35

Quantum information technologies for 6G and beyond

Editor

Prof. Merouane Debbah, Khalifa University of Science and Technology

Authors

Name	Affiliation	e-mail
Dr. Tierui Gong	Nanyang Technological University - NTU Singapore	tierui.gong@ntu.edu.sg
Dr. Yuanbin Chen	Nanyang Technological University - NTU Singapore	yuanbin.chen@ntu.edu.sg
Prof. Chau Yuen	Nanyang Technological University - NTU Singapore	chau.yuen@ntu.edu.sg
Prof. Mérouane Debbah	Khalifa University of Science and Technology, United Arab Emirates	merouane.debbah@ku.ac.ae

Version 1.0

This contribution is partly based on work performed in the framework of the WWRF. It represents the views of the authors(s) and not necessarily those of the WWRF.

Project website address: www.wwrf.ch

Abstract

The rapid progresses of quantum information technologies have been achieved from the entering of the 'second quantum evolution' era till now. Quantum information technology includes but not limited to quantum communication, quantum sensing, and quantum computing. These quantum information technologies exhibit great potential for facilitating diverse applications and their initial attempts gradually emerge, among which the quantum-domain solutions for 6G and beyond attract remarkable attention to both academia and industry.

In this white paper, we focus on the emerging and potential applications of quantum information technologies for 6G and beyond. We embrace each pillar of the quantum communication, quantum sensing, and quantum computing, and emphasize their combination with 6G and beyond, where a unified origination structure is applied to all three aspects. Specifically, we commence by a brief introduction of the fundamentals of each quantum information technology, followed by an outlook of the potential applications in 6G and beyond. We then overview the recent emerging applications of each quantum information technology to 6G and beyond, where we list representative advances from both academia and industry. We further discuss the possible challenges encountered and present a list of future directions for each quantum information technology. We finally conclude this white paper.

We briefly summarize our key findings in three aspects: Quantum communication stands out as a potent enabler for facilitating security 6G communications and network. Quantum sensing offers ground-breaking sensors, devices, and transceivers involved in 6G and beyond for facilitating high-performance communication, sensing, localization, navigation, time synchronization, and bio-inspired network monitoring, etc. Quantum computing shows its computing power advantage in solving various computationally intensive problems arising in signal processing and optimizations from various layers of 6G and beyond.

We expect that 6G and beyond will be systemically revolutionized by various quantum information technologies. To accelerate the advance, cross-domain cooperations from different research communities of academia and industry are critical for realizing the fusion. For this white paper, we expect that it can be an entry for understanding how quantum information technology and 6G fuse in the future and that it serves as benchmark for supporting continuous future research.

Table of Contents

1.	Introduction	5
1.1	Usage Scenarios and Capabilities of 6G and Beyond	5
1.2	Typical Advances of Quantum Information Technology	6
1.3	Align Quantum Information Technology with 6G KPIs.....	7
2.	Quantum Information Technology for 6G and Beyond	9
2.1	Quantum Communications for 6G and Beyond	9
2.1.1	Introduction	9
2.1.2	Applications in 6G and Beyond	9
2.1.3	Recent Advances of Quantum Communication for 6G and Beyond	10
2.1.4	Challenges	11
2.1.5	Future Directions.....	11
2.2	Quantum Sensing for 6G and Beyond	12
2.2.1	Introduction	12
2.2.2	Applications in 6G and Beyond	13
2.2.3	Recent Advances of Quantum Sensing for 6G and Beyond	14
2.2.4	Challenges	17
2.2.5	Future Directions.....	17
2.3	Quantum Computing for 6G and Beyond.....	18
2.3.1	Introduction	18
2.3.2	Applications in 6G and Beyond	19
2.3.3	Recent Advances of Quantum Computing for 6G and Beyond.....	20
2.3.4	Challenges	22
2.3.5	Future Directions.....	22
3.	Summary.....	24
4.	List of Figures	25
5.	List of Tables	26
6.	References.....	27
7.	List of Abbreviations	30

1. Introduction

1.1 Usage Scenarios and Capabilities of 6G and Beyond

The sixth-generation (6G) network is envisioned to satisfy the ever-increasing demands for new transmission schemes. The realization of 6G is planned by 2030 and its consensus of the overall framework was reached, as presented in Figure 1-1. Specifically, there are totally six usage scenarios, namely immersive communication, massive communication, hyper reliable, low-latency communication, ubiquitous connectivity, integrated artificial intelligence (AI) and communication, and integrated sensing and communication. Particularly, the former three usage scenarios are enhancements from the fifth-generation (5G) network, while the latter three ones are newly envisioned. Furthermore, there are totally 15 capabilities envisioned for 6G, where 9 capabilities are enhanced from 5G and the remaining 5 capabilities are new, as detailed in Figure 1-1. The rigorous requirements in capabilities, unprecedented network complexity, and diverse usage scenarios impose significant challenges to the realization technology of 6G. In the context of approaching the Shannon limit and Moore's Law, classical technologies may not be a sustainable candidate and the original technology innovation is essential to be seek for realizing 6G.

Usage scenarios

So called "Wheel diagram"

6 Usage scenarios

Extension from IMT-2020 (5G)

- eMBB → Immersive Communication
- mMTC → Massive Communication
- URLLC → HURLLC (Hyper Reliable & Low-Latency Communication)

New

- Ubiquitous Connectivity
- AI and Communication
- Integrated Sensing and Communication

4 Overarching aspects:

act as design principles commonly applicable to all usage scenarios

Sustainability, Connecting the unconnected, Ubiquitous intelligence, Security/resilience

Capabilities of IMT-2030

So called "Palette diagram"

The range of values given for capabilities are estimated targets for research and investigation of IMT-2030.

All values in the range have equal priority in research and investigation.

For each usage scenario, a single or multiple values within the range would be developed in future in other ITU-R Recommendations/Reports.

Figure 1-1 The envisioned usage scenarios and capabilities of 6G (ITU, 2023).

1.2 Typical Advances of Quantum Information Technology

Quantum technology has its potential to play a transformative role in the development and operation of 6G networks. With quantum principles and resources harnessed, realizing the communication, sensing, and computation purposes having capabilities far beyond their classical counterparts becomes feasible, paving the way for supporting the realization of 6G and beyond. Since the entering of the 'second quantum revolution' era, quantum communications, quantum sensing, and quantum computing constitute the three main pillars of quantum technology (Dowling & Milburn, 2003).

Initial commercial trials and products have been performed and produced. Specifically,

Quantum communications: China has built a 2000-km quantum secure communication backbone network "Beijing-Shanghai Trunk Line"¹, and has taken the lead in carrying out technical verification and application demonstration of long-distance quantum secure communication in the fields of finance, government, and electricity. Additionally, the world's first quantum science experimental satellite "Micius" has realized the satellite-to-ground quantum communication². Furthermore, British Telecom, Toshiba, and EY have realized a commercial trial of a quantum-secured metro network³. The European Space Agency (ESA), European Commission, and SES have jointly proposed the EAGLE-1 project for developing a satellite-based quantum cryptography system for European cybersecurity⁴. Additionally, the Quantum Internet Alliance (QIA) has developed a prototype quantum internet⁵. Lastly, Boeing is also promoting the quantum communication technology by using the in-space test satellite⁶. Verizon has successfully tested a quantum safe VPN for establishing encryption keys using post quantum cryptography (PQC)⁷. Besides these trails, a multitude of quantum communication products and solutions are commercially ready, such as the products for quantum key distribution (QKD) systems from the QuantumCTek (China), ID Quantique (Switzerland), Toshiba, SK Telecom, and Quantum Xchange, etc.

Quantum sensing: At the time of writing, NIST has developed world's most accurate atomic clock showing that the strontium-based timepiece gains or loses only one second every 40 billion years⁸. UK reported a successful test of un-jammable quantum navigation system, which was led by Inflection, aerospace companies BAE Systems, and QinetiQ⁹. Additionally, the latest generation magnetoencephalography system equipped with the state-of-the-art quantum magnetic sensors was delivered in Geneva, Switzerland¹⁰. Physicists from the University of Otago have used a small glass bulb

¹ http://english.scio.gov.cn/2017-09/30/content_41671118.htm

² <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature.2017.22142>

³ <https://www.global.toshiba/ww/news/corporate/2022/04/news-20220427-01.html>

⁴ https://www.esa.int/Applications/Connectivity_and_Secure_Communications/Eagle-1

⁵ <https://quantuminternetalliance.org/our-prototype-network/>

⁶ <https://investors.boeing.com/investors/news/press-release-details/2024/Boeing-Pioneering-Quantum-Communications-Technology-with-In-Space-Test-Satellite/default.aspx>

⁷ <https://www.verizon.com/about/news/verizon-quantum-safe-vpns-data>

⁸ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-024-02199-7>

⁹ <https://thequantuminsider.com/2024/05/13/uk-reports-successful-test-of-un-jammable-quantum-navigation-system/>

¹⁰ <https://evolvinglanguage.ch/geneva-at-the-heart-of-the-human-brain/>

containing an atomic vapor to demonstrate a new form of antenna for radio waves¹¹. Rydberg Technologies has demonstrated a long-range atomic wireless communication with the Rydberg atomic quantum sensor at U.S. Army NetModX23 Event¹². Just to name a few. Lastly, there are a multitude of commercial products of quantum sensors from companies, such as Campbell Scientific, Inc. (US), ID Quantique (Switzerland), LI-COR, Inc. (US), M Squared Ltd. (UK), and Muquans SAS (France), etc. The products include but not limited to atomic clocks, quantum magnetometer, quantum electrometer, quantum gravity sensors, and many others.

Quantum computing: Various areas, such as finance, pharmaceuticals, healthcare, energy, materials, logistics, telecommunications, have been explored with the aid of quantum computing. To name a few, JPMorgan Chase and AWS have optimized the large-scale portfolio management by using quantum-classical hybrid computing solutions¹³. Pfizer and XtalPi have leveraged quantum computing for facilitating the establishment of new techniques for early drug screening¹⁴. ExxonMobil and IBM has employed quantum computing for developing energy and manufacturing technologies. Furthermore, BMW Group and Pasqal have applied quantum computing to improve car design and manufacturing¹⁵. Volkswagen, taking advantage of the powerful quantum computing capability, has demonstrated the real-time optimal routing based on realistic traffic conditions¹⁶. British Telecom and D-wave have uncovered how quantum computing facilitates resource allocation and planning problems in telecommunications¹⁷. The key platforms that drive the commercial trials include but not limited to IBM quantum, D-Wave, Microsoft Azure Quantum, Google Quantum AI, Origin Quantum, QBoson, etc.

1.3 Align Quantum Information Technology with 6G KPIs

The quantum information technology is expected to be employed for providing quantum-domain solutions to 6G and beyond. The quantum properties and phenomena harnessed by quantum technologies allow these quantum-domain solutions to be more efficient and secure than their classical counterparts. In what follows, we present how quantum technologies align with 6G key performance indicators (KPIs) in terms of several critical metrics. They are specified as follows.

Latency

Quantum technologies can drastically reduce latency in 6G networks. Specifically, leveraging quantum entanglement allows instantaneous data transmission between entangled nodes, reducing communication delays from milliseconds to microseconds. Furthermore, quantum computing enhances the processing speed for network optimization, enables real-time adjustments and decision-making, and minimizes the overall latency.

¹¹ <https://www.otago.ac.nz/news/newsroom/physicists-create-new-antenna>

¹² <https://thequantuminsider.com/2023/12/22/rydberg-technologies-demonstrates-worlds-first-long-range-atomic-rf-communication-with-quantum-sensor-at-u-s-army-netmodx23-event/>

¹³ <https://thequantuminsider.com/2024/09/19/new-study-from-jpmorgan-chase-and-aws-optimizes-large-scale-portfolio-management-with-quantum-classical-hybrid-solutions/>

¹⁴ https://www.pfizer.com/news/articles/how_quantum_physics_and_ai_is_disrupting_drug_discovery_development

¹⁵ <https://thequantuminsider.com/2022/05/11/bmw-group-and-pasqal-apply-quantum-computing-to-improve-car-design-and-manufacturing/>

¹⁶ <https://lingarogroup.com/blog/when-quantum-computing-meets-supply-chain-management>

¹⁷ <https://www.dwavesys.com/resources/application/telecommunications-network-optimisation/>

Throughput

Quantum networking significantly boosts throughput by utilizing quantum superposition and entanglement, allowing multiple data streams to coexist and be transmitted simultaneously without interference.

Energy Efficiency

Quantum computing and sensors contribute to energy efficiency. Quantum computing executes complex algorithms with significantly lower energy consumption compared to classical processors. Moreover, quantum sensors provide precise monitoring and resource allocation, optimizing energy usage across the network.

Reliability and Security

Quantum technologies can enhance reliability and security. For example, QKD provides secure communication channels that are theoretically immune to eavesdropping, significantly enhancing data security. Quantum-enhanced error correction and network protocols ensure higher uptime and more robust network performance. For instance, increasing uptime from 99.999% to 99.99999% translates to a reduction in downtime from approximately 5.26 minutes per year to ~0.0053 minutes per year. Implementing QKD ensures that any attempt to intercept communication alters the quantum states, immediately signalling a security breach.

Network Capacity and Scalability

Quantum technologies allow for unprecedented network scalability. Specifically, quantum superposition enables multiple data channels within the same frequency band, exponentially increasing network capacity. Quantum sensing and quantum computing manage a higher density of devices efficiently, supporting the Internet of Everything (IoE) with up to 100 million devices per square kilometre.

To summarize, we list them in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1 Quantum information technologies with 6G KPIs

KPI	Current 5G level	Expected 6G level	With quantum technologies	Improvement
Latency	Average: ~1 ms Peak: ~0.5 ms	Average: ~0.1 ms Peak: ~0.05 ms	Average: <0.1 μs Peak: ~0.01 μs	10,000× reduction (avg) 5,000× reduction (peak)
Throughput	Peak: ~20 Gbps Sustained: ~10 Gbps	Peak: ~1 Tbps Sustained: ~500 Gbps	Peak: ~10 Tbps Sustained: ~5 Tbps	500× increase (both peak and sustained)
Energy efficiency	~1 pJ/bit	~0.1 pJ/bit	~0.01 pJ/bit	10× improvement over classical 6G 100× over 5G
Reliability	~99.999% uptime	~99.9999% uptime	~99.99999% uptime	Two additional nines in uptime
Security	Standard encryption	Enhanced encryption	QKD	Theoretically unbreakable encryption
Device density	~1 million devices/km ²	~10 million devices/km ²	~100 million devices/km ²	10× increase over classical 6G 100× over 5G

2. Quantum Information Technology for 6G and Beyond

As presented above, the potential of quantum information technology have initially demonstrated by early applications. In the following of this white paper, we will embrace each of them with an emphasis on how they facilitate 6G and beyond. We present their contents in order of quantum communication, quantum sensing, and quantum computing.

2.1 Quantum Communications for 6G and Beyond

2.1.1 Introduction

Quantum communication has emerged as a transformative technology for achieving secure, high-capacity, and ultra-reliable data transmission, making it a crucial component in the development of future communication networks. As 5G networks continue to evolve and 6G begins to take shape, researchers around the world are increasingly interested in exploring how quantum information technologies can be integrated into these systems. Quantum communication, leveraging principles of quantum mechanics such as quantum entanglement and QKD, offers an alternative to classical cryptographic methods and has the potential to revolutionize communication security and efficiency. This literature review summarizes recent advances in quantum communication, specifically in the context of 5G, 6G, and beyond, highlighting major achievements, challenges, and future prospects.

QKD is one of the most well-known applications of quantum communication, providing a theoretically unbreakable method for secure key exchange. Unlike classical key distribution methods, QKD relies on the properties of quantum mechanics, such as the no-cloning theorem and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, to ensure that any attempt to eavesdrop on the key exchange will be detectable. This unique feature makes QKD particularly attractive for securing communication links in the face of the growing threat posed by quantum computers, which have the potential to break many of the cryptographic protocols currently in use. Over the past decade, QKD has been successfully implemented in various scenarios, from point-to-point fiber optic links to satellite-based communication, and it continues to be a key focus of research for enhancing the security of future communication networks.

2.1.2 Applications in 6G and Beyond

Quantum Communications in 5G

Over the past decade, investigations on quantum communications have focused on integrating quantum information technologies into the existing 5G infrastructure. QKD has drawn significant attention as a way of enhancing the security of 5G networks. (Pirandola et al, 2020) outlines a comprehensive QKD network architecture that can be layered onto classical 5G infrastructure, allowing for secure encryption key exchange. The integration of QKD with classical protocols, such as IPsec and TLS, has been a major focus, and research has shown that these combined systems can effectively counter quantum computing threats (Mao et al, 2018).

China has made substantial progress in integrating QKD into terrestrial 5G networks. A hybrid QKD-5G model was proposed in which quantum signals coexist with classical data over fiber optic infrastructure, achieving both secure communication and improved throughput. Experimental results from these implementations have demonstrated the practicality of QKD for securing backhaul communication links.

Internationally, the European Union's OpenQKD project has aimed to develop and test QKD in metropolitan environments using 5G technology. Researchers have successfully demonstrated the feasibility of implementing QKD over long distances by optimizing error correction and increasing the key rate to accommodate real-time applications (Chiti et al, 2022).

Quantum Communications in 6G

6G aims to provide ultra-reliable, low-latency, and high-capacity communication to support emerging applications such as the IoE, holographic multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) communications (Chen et al, 2024), (Gong et al, 2024), and autonomous systems. Quantum communications are envisioned to play a key role in addressing some of the core challenges faced by 6G (Mao et al, 2018).

Quantum entanglement distribution and quantum repeaters are critical components for achieving the high reliability required by 6G networks. By leveraging low Earth orbit (LEO) satellites, the authors in (Yin et al, 2017) successfully demonstrated quantum entanglement distribution over a distance of 1,200 km, laying the foundation for large-scale quantum networks that could be applied to 6G architectures.

In addition to entanglement distribution, the concept of quantum-secured edge computing has emerged as an important area of research. (Prateek et al, 2023) proposed integrating quantum communication into 6G edge networks to ensure the privacy of distributed computations. By employing quantum teleportation techniques, this approach mitigates vulnerabilities associated with traditional edge computing architectures, enhancing the security of sensitive data in 6G-enabled services.

The inherent quantum parallelism could also help improve the efficiency of 6G communication. For example, (Mehic et al, 2023) explored how quantum Fourier transform algorithms can optimize resource allocation in 6G, potentially reducing latency in dense environments. The use of quantum algorithms for network optimization presents a promising direction to meet 6G's performance demands.

2.1.3 Recent Advances of Quantum Communication for 6G and Beyond

Quantum satellite communications: Recent advances in quantum satellite communication, such as the successful deployment of the Micius satellite by China, represent a major step towards achieving global quantum communication (Yin et al, 2017). This satellite has demonstrated the ability to perform QKD with ground stations over long distances, providing the blueprint for satellite-based quantum communication in 6G networks.

Quantum repeaters: Another important milestone is the advancement in quantum repeaters and entanglement swapping protocols. (Azuma et al, 2023) (Sangouard et al, 2011) have made significant progress in developing quantum repeater technologies that extend the transmission range of quantum signals, which is crucial for establishing large-scale quantum networks. These repeaters overcome the challenges posed by photon loss and decoherence, paving the way for reliable long-distance quantum communication.

Quantum-secured Internet of Things (IoT): Quantum-secured IoT applications have also gained traction (Fernández-Caramés et al, 2019). (Deepanramkumar et al, 2024) proposed a framework for integrating QKD with IoT devices in a 6G environment, ensuring secure communication between billions of interconnected devices. This approach highlights the potential of quantum communication in securing the vast number of devices in future IoT ecosystems.

Quantum error correction (QEC): QEC techniques are another area of rapid advancement. (Fowler et al, 2012) demonstrated surface code error correction methods

that could be applied to quantum communication systems to enhance their robustness. QEC is essential for overcoming noise and maintaining the integrity of quantum information, especially in practical 6G environments where quantum systems will need to operate continuously over extended periods.

Quantum-classical communication protocols: The development of hybrid quantum-classical communication protocols is also noteworthy. (Van Meter and Touch, 2013) explored hybrid architectures where quantum communication is integrated with classical networks to optimize resource utilization and improve scalability. This hybrid approach is particularly promising for 6G networks, where the coexistence of quantum and classical systems will be necessary.

Quantum random number generation (QRNG): Furthermore, advancements in QRNG have contributed to secure communication in 6G. (Liu et al, 2018) presented high-speed, device-independent QRNG systems that generate true random numbers based on quantum phenomena, which are essential for cryptographic applications in future communication networks.

The use of quantum teleportation in 6G networks is also being explored to enhance data privacy. (Wang et al, 2022) proposed using quantum teleportation for secure data transmission in a distributed 6G network architecture. This method provides an additional layer of security by ensuring that data is transmitted without physically moving the qubits, thus mitigating interception risks.

2.1.4 Challenges

The challenges in implementing quantum communications for 6G Networks and beyond are outlined in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1 Challenges of quantum communications for 6G and beyond

Challenges	Description
Scalability of Quantum Systems	Quantum repeaters are needed to extend the range of quantum communication beyond the limits imposed by photon losses. Repeaters are still in the experimental phase (Duan et al, 2022).
Coexistence of Quantum and Classical Data	The coexistence of quantum and classical data within the same communication infrastructure introduces channel interference. (Wang et al, 2020) suggested wavelength division multiplexing techniques to minimize interference.
Quantum-Resistant Cryptography	Quantum-resistant cryptographic solutions are needed to maintain compatibility with quantum-secured links. Researchers are exploring hybrid approaches where QKD is used for key exchange, while post-quantum cryptography handles data encryption.

2.1.5 Future Directions

Quantum communication is still a rapidly evolving field, and several exciting directions hold promise for the future. Below are some of the key areas where further research and development are expected.

Quantum Repeaters and Long-Distance Quantum Networks

The continued development of quantum repeaters is essential for the scalability of quantum networks. More efficient and robust quantum repeater designs are needed to minimize photon loss and extend the range of quantum communication. This could facilitate the realization of a global quantum internet, which is expected to be a crucial part of 6G.

Quantum Internet and Satellite-Based Communication

Leveraging satellites for quantum communication remains an area of great interest. The success of the Micius satellite has opened new possibilities for global QKD and entanglement distribution. Further research will aim to improve the efficiency of satellite-based quantum communication, including the integration of LEO and geostationary orbit (GEO) satellites for continuous global coverage.

Quantum-Enabled Meta-Surfaces (QeMS)

Inspired by the concept of QeMS, this may be a novel direction that aims to dynamically manipulate quantum signals using meta-surfaces in real time. Furthermore, more meta-surface-based architecture should also be considered, such as holographic meta-surfaces, stacked intelligent meta-surfaces (SIM), etc. These surfaces can be used for adaptive beamforming, enhanced security, and improved signal strength, making them highly valuable for 6G networks.

Hybrid Quantum-Classical Architectures

Hybrid architectures that combine quantum and classical communication technologies will be critical for the practical deployment of quantum communication systems in 6G. Research is needed to design effective protocols for managing the coexistence of quantum and classical signals over shared infrastructure, ensuring both efficiency and security (Van Meter and Touch, 2013).

Quantum Security for IoT

Quantum-secured IoT communication is expected to play a major role in 6G, given the vast number of interconnected devices. Integrating QKD into IoT frameworks to ensure secure communication between devices will be a key focus area.

2.2 Quantum Sensing for 6G and Beyond

2.2.1 Introduction

As one of the key pillars of quantum information technology, quantum sensing relies on the exploit of various quantum phenomena and/or properties to perform a measurement of a physical quantity. The physical quantity is connected to the intrinsic properties of microscopic particles during the measurements. This unique measurement manner is less influenced by extrinsic perturbations, thereby exhibiting a quite stable measurement having an unprecedented sensitivity. Quantum sensing encompasses but not limited to quantum precision measurement and quantum metrology.

In the following of this section, we will first present the basic principle of quantum sensing, followed by the representative quantum sensing technologies.

Quantum sensing principle

Figure 2-1 The typical three-stage quantum sensing principle (Kitching et al, 2011)

The basic principle of quantum sensing constitutes three procedures, namely, quantum state preparation, quantum state evolution, and quantum state readout, as depicted in Figure 2-1.

Quantum state preparation: The purpose is to prepare the ‘atoms’ used for sensing to a well-defined state, which allows further measurement and state evolution.

Quantum state evolution: The prepared quantum state will evolve under the influence of the physical quantity, such as electric fields, magnetic fields, etc., to be measured.

Quantum state readout: The evolved quantum state will be readout, so that the physical quantity to be measured, a function of the evolved quantum state, can be extracted.

Representative Technologies of Quantum Sensing

There are several representative technologies for realizing quantum sensing, such as neutral atoms, solid-state spins, superconducting circuits, and trapped ions. In the following, we emphasize the first three of these technologies that are quite relevant to 6G and beyond at the time of writing, as shown in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2 Representative technologies for realizing quantum sensing

Technology	Description	Applications	Advantages
Neutral atoms	Highly excited atoms in the vapor cell for detecting external electric and magnetic fields	Wireless communication and sensing, remote sensing and imaging, long-distance and large-scale network synchronous, high-precision localization and navigation	High sensitivity, room temperature operation
Solid-state spins	Electron or nuclear spins for detecting magnetic and electric fields	Bio-inspired wireless sensor networks, high-precision localization and navigation	High sensitivity, room temperature operation
Superconducting	Utilizing superconducting materials to create, manipulate, and measure quantum states	Quantum radar enabled wireless sensing	High sensitivity

2.2.2 Applications in 6G and Beyond

Quantum sensing, leveraging quantum mechanics principles to achieve unprecedented precision in measurements, is expected to play a transformative role in the development and operation of 6G and beyond. Its compelling features are capable of facilitating a wide of applications in communication, sensing, localization, navigation, and many others in 6G and beyond. We present the representative applications as follows

Quantum sensors for wireless communication and sensing: As wireless transmissions rely on the electromagnetic (EM) wave detection, it is critical for wireless systems having a high-precision EM field detection. The conventional wireless systems employ EM antennas that produce a corresponding signal current driven by the received EM fields, which have a low sensitivity. By harnessing the quantum principles for facilitating high-precision measurements, advanced quantum sensors, such as Rydberg

atomic quantum sensors (RAQs) and quantum radar, are capable of overcoming the conventional limitations of wireless communication and sensing.

Quantum inertial measurement for high-precision localization and navigation: As vehicle-to-everything (V2X) and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) enabled communication and networking are expected to be prevalent in 6G and beyond. There are a vast of requirements of the localization and navigation for vehicles and drones. The conventional global navigation satellite system (GNSS) based methods are less accurate and may fail in the GNSS absent scenarios. Furthermore, those relying on conventional inertial measurement units may face significant errors and require continuous calibrations. By contrast, the quantum inertial measurement units, e.g., atomic gyroscope and atomic accelerometer, are capable of providing enhanced location and navigation performance without requiring any GNSS assistance.

Quantum atomic clocks for long-distance and large-scale network synchronous: As 6G and beyond will be a space-air-ground-sea network for fulfilling the seamless accessible requirement from any location, it is foreseeable that the future 6G network exhibits a long-distance and large-scale feature. For those tasks and protocols heavily relying on the precise clock synchronous, it is considerably important to realize the time and frequency synchronous. The quantum atomic clocks serve as a promising solution, which are capable of offering precise and stable reference signals for network synchronous.

Quantum magnetic sensing for bio-inspired wireless sensor networks: As a promising solution for magnetic sensing, atomic magnetometers allow a more precise sensing performance than the conventional magnetic sensing schemes, which are beneficial for health monitoring. They also have the potential to be constructed in lightweight wearable biosensors to facilitate the bio-inspired wireless sensor networks.

To summarize, we list these main applications in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3 Quantum sensing application in 6G and beyond

Functionality	Quantum sensing candidate	Application in 6G and beyond
Communication and sensing	RAQs, quantum radars	Advanced quantum sensors for wireless communication and sensing
Localization and navigation	Quantum accelerometers and gyroscopes	High-precision localization and navigation without GNSS
Time synchronization	Atomic clocks	Long-distance and large-scale network precise synchronous
Bio-signal monitoring	Quantum bio-magnetic sensors	Bio-inspired wireless sensor networks

2.2.3 Recent Advances of Quantum Sensing for 6G and Beyond

In the following of this section, we present the existing advances of several emerging applications to 6G and beyond. These advances mainly include the RAQs and quantum radar empowered schemes. For the rest quantum schemes mentioned in the former section, they exhibit great potential for 6G and beyond, but their studies have not been extensively performed. Therefore, we focus more on the former two application advances. The details are as follows.

Rydberg atomic quantum receivers (RAQRs) for wireless communication and sensing in 6G and beyond: The Rydberg atoms have the potential to be harnessed for constructing advanced wireless receivers for 6G due to their compelling advantages in sensing external electric fields. This will facilitate the realization of RAQR-aided wireless communications and sensing (Gong et al, 2024).

RAQRs have numerous compelling advantages over the conventional EM antennas, such as their extremely high sensitivity, wideband tunability, international system of units (SI) traceability, and compact form factor. These prominent features of RAQRs make them appealing in assisting classical wireless communications and sensing. Many experimental studies from the physics community have been performed. They focused on improving the sensitivity, and developing multi-band or continuous-band detection. They also realize various functionalities, such as detection of amplitude, phase, polarization, modulation, spatial direction, and spatial displacement. Furthermore, several initial applications for verifying RAQRs in assisting communications were experimentally presented in (Meyer et al, 2018), (Cai et al, 2023), (Yuan et al, 2023), (Zhang et al, 2024). The above experimental studies have demonstrated the feasibility of RAQRs.

To further facilitate the application of this technology to 6G and beyond, the study of (Gong & Sun et al, 2024) constructed an end-to-end RAQR-aided wireless reception scheme, as demonstrated in Figure 2-2, and proposed a corresponding input-output equivalent baseband signal model of the overall system. This signal model paves the way for performing various signal processing and optimization algorithms in a convenient way. The study further unveiled the performance of RAQR-aided wireless communication and sensing, where the results showcased that the RAQRs are capable of providing a significant gain in terms of the receive signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) compared to its conventional counterparts. Furthermore, the work (Gong & Yuen & See et al, 2024) presented a RAQ-MIMO system, where multiple receive elements are prepared for simultaneously serving multiple communication users. This study constructed a corresponding signal model and performed the system capacity for the RAQ-MIMO system. The results showcased that the significant transmit power reduction or the alternative capacity enhancement are possible by RAQ-MIMO compared to the conventional massive MIMO systems. Further employing the multiple sensors constituted by Rydberg atoms, another work (Gong & Yuen, 2024) verified the capability of RAQRs in performing the detection of direction of arrivals (DOAs) of multiple targets. The results exhibited the significant reduction of the DOA estimation error compared to its conventional counterpart.

Figure 2-2 The RAQR-aided wireless reception scheme (Gong & Sun et al, 2024).

RAQs for near-field imaging and remote sensing: Exploiting the benefits of Rydberg atoms, the RAQs have been demonstrated their feasibility for near-field imaging in (Wade et al, 2017) and for remote sensing of soil moisture in (Arumugam et al, 2024). Specifically, the work (Wade et al, 2017) presented a Terahertz-to-optical conversion using the RAQs, which is capable of realizing real-time near-field Terahertz field imaging. By contrast, the work (Arumugam et al, 2024) realizes the remote sensing of soil moisture only relying on the existing satellite radio signals. This further facilitates the application of RAQs to a multitude of remote sensing tasks, such as water cycle and sea level monitoring, weather and air monitoring, and many other tasks for earth ecosystem and military purposes.

RAQs for EM field probe and EM antenna calibration: From the operating principle of the conventional EM antennas, it is known that the EM antennas require specific calibrations to guarantee their precision. However, the calibrations are typically performed in the known EM environment that is conversely required to be measured by well-calibrated antennas. This cycling will lead to a so-called ‘chicken-or-egg’ dilemma. By contrast, the SI-traceability of RAQs can be harnessed for acquiring precise measurements for probing EM fields without any calibration (Holloway et al, 2014). The accuracy of EM field probe facilitates the calibration of EM antennas.

Quantum radar for sensing and localization: Sensing and localization will become a necessary requirement in 6G and beyond. Quantum radar may become a radical solution because of its high sensitivity, noise immunity, enhanced spatial resolution, and low detectability compared to the conventional radar systems. It relies on the use of the principle of quantum entanglement, which will push the conventional limit and may reach the Heisenberg limit. The emergence of the quantum illumination concept was proposed in (Lloyd, 2008). After that the development of quantum radar are detailed in (Luong et al, 2023).

Advances from industry: The significant industrial advances of RAQs have been achieved. For example, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) has promoted a Science of Atomic Vapors for New Technologies (SAVaNT) program and an Enhancing Quantum Sensor Technologies with Rydberg Atoms (EQSTRA) program for facilitating the capabilities, technology readiness level, and application of Rydberg-based quantum sensors. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) has facilitated its quantum Rydberg radar system for surface, topography, and vegetation. Furthermore, the Global telecoms operator BT Group (London, U.K.) has conducted trials of its new quantum radio receiver in 2022 to enhance the capabilities of next-generation 5G and IoT networks. The Rydberg technologies company has demonstrated the long-range atomic RF communication during the Network Modernization Experiment 2023 (NetModX23) event at the U.S. Army Combat Capabilities Development Command (DEVCOM) C5ISR Centre¹⁸. At the same time, the Infleqion company has demonstrated its quantum radio frequency aperture/receiver system, called sqyWire, at the army C5ISR NetModX23 evaluation¹⁹.

The significant progresses of quantum radar have also been achieved from the industry since its emergence. Validation and initial commercialization have been demonstrated. For example, the first Chinese quantum radar was demonstrated in 2016 by the 14th Institute in China Electronics Technology Group Corporation (CETC)²⁰. The particulate optical quantum radar and high-resolution velocity azimuth display (VAD) lidar from the

¹⁸ <https://thequantuminsider.com/2023/12/22/rydberg-technologies-demonstrates-worlds-first-long-range-atomic-rf-communication-with-quantum-sensor-at-u-s-army-netmodx23-event/>

¹⁹ <https://www.infleqion.com/news/infleqions-quantum-rf-solution-excels-at-army-c5isr-netmodx23-assessment>

²⁰ <https://web.archive.archive.unhcr.org/20230521073928/https://www.refworld.org/docid/59bb93324.html>

QuantumCTek company. The quantum gas Lidar from the QLM company, and the quantum photonic vibrometer from the Quantum Computing Inc (QCI) company²¹.

2.2.4 Challenges

For RAQSSs, the challenges are mainly from the impairments of physical implementations. For instance, RAQSSs rely on optical laser sources for Rydberg atom preparations. The laser stability, lower laser noise and power consumption, and miniaturization of laser equipment are critical for practical applications. Additionally, the reception of wideband signals is not ready for practical wireless communication and sensing. The realization of a continuous frequency band detection by using the discrete Rydberg energy levels is not straightforward.

For quantum interferometric radars, the generation of specific state may be challenging for large photons due to the fragile of the state, especially in the presence of loss. For quantum illumination radars, the generation of entangled signals and the implementation of joint measurements may be challenging. Quantum two-mode squeezing (QTMS) radars are simplified quantum illumination radars, all requiring cryogenic refrigeration, which is challenging for practical applications.

For other quantum sensing schemes related to 6G and beyond, such as quantum inertial measurements, atomic clocks, and quantum magnetic measurements, their studies are mainly performed from the sensor's perspective, which cannot be readily applied to 6G and beyond. The maturity of these quantum sensing technologies for better performance is also under developments.

2.2.5 Future Directions

To overcome the challenges and facilitate the potential and applications, more future efforts are required. Hence, we list several future directions as follows.

Improved performance and efficiency: As the ever-increasing demands on better quantum sensing performance are always required for many applications, so that continuously pushing the current sensing performance to higher levels becomes one of the main future directions. At the same time, better performance should be achieved in an effective manner, enabling improved efficiency quantum sensing solutions.

Low SWaP-C quantum sensing solution: For facilitating the maturity of quantum sensing technologies, their physical implementations need to be achieved at the commercial standard, e.g., retaining lower size, weight, power, and cost (SWaP-C). Low SWaP-C solutions are critical for enabling broader applications because there are many realistic restrictions, such as size/weight/power/cost limitations, imposing to the quantum-assisted systems.

Use cases, models, signal processing, and optimization for 6G: For facilitating the seamless blend between quantum sensing and 6G network, typical use cases can provide more insights on how quantum sensing facilitates 6G and beyond, and also on exploring the application boundary of quantum sensing in 6G and beyond. Additionally, the corresponding models, signal processing and optimization approaches need to be constructed and developed for bridging different research communities and promoting a multitude of upper-level designs.

Integration with other technologies: As 6G and beyond will be an evolution from conventional infrastructures, the quantum sensing technology requires to be compatible to existing technologies and infrastructures. Furthermore, it is foreseeable that the future 6G and beyond will be a complex system combining a multitude of different emerging

²¹ <https://icvtank.oss-ap-southeast-1.aliyuncs.com/QUANTUM-REPORTS/Quantum%20Radar%20Report.pdf>

technologies, such as AI and new materials. The perfect fusion between quantum sensing and them is capable of uncovering the full potential from a systemic perspective.

2.3 Quantum Computing for 6G and Beyond

2.3.1 Introduction

Quantum computing is a revolutionary technique of employing the quantum mechanical principles for realizing an extremely-fast computing speedup for specific computing problems. Different from the convention computing, quantum computing relies on the qubit, the superposition state, and the entanglement, which offers a natural parallel computing paradigm and allows a simultaneous process of a large amount of information. In the following of this section, we will first present the elementaries of quantum computing, followed by its representative technologies.

Elementary of quantum computing

The basic element of quantum computing is qubit. It can represent any combination of 0 and 1 by using the superposition principle. The superposition allows quantum computing to explore multiple solutions simultaneously. Additionally, the multiple qubits can be correlated with each other through the entanglement, which allows efficient information sharing for supporting various quantum computing algorithms. The realization of qubit manipulations is enabled by the quantum gates, which are analogous to the logic gates in conventional computing. But the difference is that quantum gates are always reversible. Typical quantum gates include but limited to

1-qubit gates: Pauli-I, X, Y, Z gates, Hadamard (H) gate, phase gate, and T gate;

2-qubit gates: Controlled not (CNOT) gate, controlled Z gate and SWAP gate;

Multi-qubit gates: Toffoli gate (3-qubit) and the universal gates constructed by H, CNOT, and T gates.

Built upon the quantum gates, the quantum circuit is a sequence of quantum gates, which is capable of information processing. The quantum circuits are intrinsically safe to any attempt of copying and measuring. The realization of quantum circuits is challenging and not scalable at the time of writing. There are several representative technologies for constructing quantum circuits, as detailed in the following section. The typical operation flow of quantum computing is as follows.

Initialization: The qubits are initialized in specific starting states.

Quantum operations: A series of quantum gates are applied in the form of quantum circuits for generating superposition, entanglement, and perform quantum computing.

Interference and amplification: The desired solution is amplified while the incorrectness is cancelling out by leveraging the interference.

Measurement: The qubits are measured once the quantum computation is completed, where the quantum states collapse to classical outcomes (0/1 for each qubit) having their corresponding probabilities.

Post-processing: Classical post-processing is performed for the resulting measurements to obtain the required result.

Representative Technologies of Quantum Computing

There are several representative technologies for realizing the quantum circuits of quantum computing. We list them in Table 2-4 by presenting certain critical metrics (e.g.,

coherence time, gate speed, number of qubits, qubit fidelity), their scalability, and operating temperature.

Table 2-4 Representative technologies for realizing quantum computing

Technology	Coherence time	Gate speed	Number of qubits (2024)	Qubit fidelity (1-qubit / 2-qubit)	Scalability	Operating temperature
Superconducting	Microseconds (10–100 μ s)	Fast (10–100 ns)	50–1100+	~99.9% / ~99%	Moderate	Cryogenic
Photonic system	Seconds (limited by photons)	Fast (10–100 ns)	70–500+ (scalable)	~99.9% (single photon process)	High	Room temperature
Trapped ions	Seconds (1–10 s)	Slow (μ s to ms)	20–500+	~99.99% / ~99.7%	Moderate	Room temperature
Neutral atoms	Seconds (1–10 s)	Moderate (1–10 μ s)	100–1200+	~99.5% / ~97%	High	Room temperature
Quantum dots	Milliseconds (10–100 ms)	Moderate (10–100 μ s)	10–50	~99.9% / ~90%	High (silicon-based)	Cryogenic
NV centers in diamond	Milliseconds (1–10 ms)	Slow (μ s to ms)	1–10 (small scale)	~99.9% (single qubit)	Low	Room temperature
Topological system	Long (theoretical protection)	Not yet demonstrated	0 (experimental stage)	Not yet demonstrated	High (if realized)	Cryogenic

2.3.2 Applications in 6G and Beyond

In order to satisfy the ever-increasing demands on a large amount of data transmission, massive communication and ubiquitous connectivity, ultra-high reliable and low-latency communication, and on a multi-functional intelligent network, 6G and beyond are planned. They are envisioned to assist extremely-high data-rate transmissions for supporting immersive communications, constituting ubiquitous space-air-ground-sea connectivity, and forming a communication, sensing, computing, control, and AI-integrated network. These requirements inspire a large amount of computing requirements. To satisfy these requirements, quantum computing becomes a promising solution. The applications of quantum computing to 6G and beyond are depicted in Figure 2-3 and are detailed as follows

Figure 2-3 Quantum computing applications in 6G and beyond.

Quantum computing for the physical layer: The physical layer of 6G and beyond will encompass massive signal processing tasks, such as large-scale channel estimation, beamforming, signal detection, and coding and modulation. The requirements of computing for these tasks are of a huge amount. This is due to the considerable increase of signal dimension and the significant computational complexity increase of signal processing and optimization algorithms caused by this dimension increase. For example, the massive MIMO and its evolutions, such as stacked intelligent metasurfaces and holographic MIMO, involve a multitude of antenna elements, which results in a large-scale signal dimension that require higher computing capability for those signal processing tasks stated above.

Quantum computing for the network layer: The network of 6G and beyond will become more complex in terms of its architecture, constitution, and resource types due to the ubiquitous connectivity and multi-functional fusion of the network. To meet better network performance, joint network optimizations across the architecture, constitutions, and resources become crucial. These optimization tasks possibly undergo large-scale distribution, heterogeneous structure, diverse but restricted resources, and strongly-coupled optimization variables. Optimization algorithms and AI networks may become promising solutions, but effectively performing these tasks requires the support of a powerful computing capability.

Quantum computing for the application layer: The application layer of 6G and beyond will be capable of supporting a multitude of diverse businesses and scenarios, such as immersive entertainments, smart industry and robotics, digital twins, and critical communications. The required quality of service (QoS) and quality of experience (QoE) is different for different businesses and scenarios. It is essential to optimize the coordination of the diverse businesses and scenarios while guaranteeing their QoS and QoE, which requires a powerful computing capability.

Quantum computing for AI assisted solutions for all layers: For all the above layers of 6G and beyond, AI exhibits a promising solution for realizing signal processing and optimization. For example, AI is capable of performing the physical layer signal processing in a joint fashion, exhibiting a better performance than the conventional block-separated fashion. AI can also facilitate various complicated network optimizations, business predictions, and many others. However, powerful computing capability is needed for AI, especially for the large language models (LLMs).

2.3.3 Recent Advances of Quantum Computing for 6G and Beyond

Performed upon the quantum circuits, quantum computing algorithms are the essential ingredient for realizing the various quantum computing tasks. In the following of this section, we first present the existing quantum computing algorithms that are particularly potential for 6G and beyond. Then we present several emerging applications of quantum computing to 6G and beyond.

First, we present the representative quantum computing algorithms in **Table 2-5** in terms of a brief description, applicable problems, and applications to 6G and beyond.

Table 2-5 Representative algorithms for realizing quantum computing

Algorithm	Description	Applicable problems	Applications to 6G and beyond
Quantum Fourier Transform (QFT)	Computing the discrete Fourier transform with exponential speedup	Discrete Fourier transform	Quantum signal processing for the physical layer
Shor's Algorithm	Factorizing large integers and finding discrete logarithms with exponential speedup	Prime factorization of large numbers	Channel estimation, detection, and localization in the physical layer (Botsinis et al, 2018), network routing and privacy protection protocol design in the network layer (Qu et al, 2023)
Grover's Algorithm	Searching for a target in an unstructured dataset	Optimization problems having unstructured solutions	
Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA)	Solving combinatorial optimization problems by approximating the best solution	Routing, scheduling, and resource allocation	Coding in the physical layer (Kasi et al, 2024), network optimization across routing and resource allocation in the network layer (Mastroianni et al, 2024)
Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE)	Finding the ground state of a quantum system using a variational approach	Resource allocation	Resource allocation in the network layer (Mastroianni et al, 2024)
Harrow Hassidim Lloyd (HHL) Algorithm	Solving linear systems of equations with exponential speedup	Large-scale linear equations	Quantum machine learning for AI assisted solutions for all layers of 6G and beyond (Zaman et al, 2023), (Tariq et al, 2024)
Quantum Neural Networks (QNN)	Implementing neural networks using quantum circuits for faster training and inference	Deep learning applications	

Then, there are emerging applications of quantum computing to 6G and beyond, which are presented as follows:

Quantum machine intelligence for 6G ultra-reliable & low-latency communication (URLLC): As URLLC will be a stringent requirement in 6G and beyond for supporting the mission-critical applications, efficient and intelligent scheduling design is critical. To facilitate such a scheduling scheme design, the QAOA method is employed in (Zaman et al, 2023) by taking advantage of the quantum computing speedup. Specifically, the scheduling scheme design is formulated as a combinatorial problem that can be solved

through the QAOA. Consequently, the computational overhead of task offloading and resource management can be reduced. Furthermore, this work adopts the QNNs for reducing the computational complexity of dynamic channel allocation and for achieving URLLC of a complex heterogeneous network design.

Hybrid deep quantum transformer networks (QTNs) for predicting ISAC optimal beams: High beam training overhead inevitably occurs for large antenna arrays when operating at high frequency bands. The work (Tariq et al, 2024) presented a hybrid deep QTN scheme for predicting the optical beam by jointly exploiting the received sensory data from the base station and the position-based data from the user terminals. The experimental results showcased the low complexity and high performance of the QTN scheme.

QAOA based decoder for channel codes: The forward error correction (FEC) is critical for guaranteeing the reliable transmission of wireless communications, but needs significant computing resources. To attain the performance but reduce the complexity, the work (Kasi et al, 2024) presented a QAOA based FEC decoder for low density parity check (LDPC) and polar codes. The result showcased the scheme realizes successful decoding having an error performance equivalent to the state-of-the art classical decoder at low code block lengths.

Advances from industry: British Telecom and D-wave have uncovered how quantum computing facilitates resource allocation and planning problems in telecommunications²². Additionally, QBoson company cooperating with China Mobile have dedicated in offering quantum computing solutions for computing power scheduling²³ and MIMO beam selection²⁴. Furthermore, Cinfo and Kipu Quantum and R have employed quantum computing to improve the Galician operator's optical fiber backbone network²⁵. In summary, the application of quantum computing to future 6G and beyond is in its fancy. More efforts are required for facilitating the developments of quantum-domain solutions.

2.3.4 Challenges

The challenges of quantum computing for 6G and beyond are of several aspects. Specifically, the current noisy intermediate scale quantum (NISQ) computing platforms face the scalability and hardware limitations, which are not ready for large-scale 6G computing tasks due to the limitations of the coherence time, number of qubits, and the quantum gate fidelity. They also suffer from high SWaP-C restricted by the current computing hardware developments. Furthermore, these quantum computing platforms are also sensitive to the noise contamination that will cause inaccurate or even incorrect computing results. Lastly, the integration of quantum computing to classical systems may be complex due to the cross-paradigm transmission. Particularly, the existing quantum computing algorithms may not be readily for the use cases of 6G and beyond.

2.3.5 Future Directions

To further facilitate wide applications of quantum computing in 6G and beyond, we list several future directions as follows.

²² <https://www.dwavesys.com/resources/application/telecommunications-network-optimisation/>

²³ <https://www.qboson.com/solution?id=28>

²⁴ <https://www.qboson.com/newsDetail?id=208>

²⁵ <https://thequantuminsider.com/2024/01/24/quantum-algorithm-can-be-used-to-optimize-telecommunication-networks/#:~:text=Quantum%20Algorithm%20Can%20be%20Used%20to%20Optimize,with%20current%20quantum%20technology%20and%20anticipate%20counteractions.>

Hardware platform: As a fundamental quantum computing carrier, the current hardware platforms are not mature enough to support its quantum supremacy. It is important to design high-fidelity qubits, fault-tolerant and scalable quantum circuits and architectures for realizing mature quantum computing platforms having millions of fault-tolerant qubits. Also, with inaccurate or incorrect measurements, quantum error correction is deserved for building robust and large-scale quantum computing systems. For facilitating a wide variety of commercial applications, the low SWaP-C standard should also be satisfied.

Algorithmic development: As the current quantum computing platforms fail to support many of the quantum algorithms in a pure quantum manner, the quantum algorithms need to be tailored for effectively proceeding on the so-called NISQ platforms. It is of great significance to develop quantum algorithms for classical challenging tasks while only leveraging limited quantum resources from now to a long period of time.

Hybrid classical-quantum computing: Before stepping into the pure quantum stage, the coexistence of both quantum computing and classical computing become predictable for a long period of time. To effectively combine both sides, the hybrid classical-quantum computing is necessary for practical applications. Intelligent task partitioning, efficient interaction, coordination, and control are critical aspects.

6G-adapted quantum computing: To sufficiently uncover the advantage of quantum computing for 6G and beyond, specific computing problems should be properly extracted and formulated from different 6G tasks, such as signal processing in the physical layer, resource allocation, routing, network management and optimization in the network layer, and diverse businesses prediction and coordination in the application layer. Effective and efficient 6G-adapted quantum computing schemes should be developed obeying the various network resource constraints. They also need to retain the security, flexibility, and scalability for various 6G tasks, and can be extended to the pure quantum-domain solutions.

3. Summary

The objectives of this white paper is to present a comprehensive overview of the recent advances of quantum information technologies (quantum communication, quantum sensing, and quantum computing) for 6G and beyond, and outlook the potent fusion between them. The key findings are as follows. First, the quantum communication technologies stand out as a potent enabler for facilitating security 6G communications and network. Furthermore, the quantum sensing technologies exhibit as a groundbreaking solution for various sensors, devices, and transceivers involved in future 6G and beyond, facilitating high performance measurements of a multitude of physical quantities. Lastly, the quantum computing technologies show their computing power advantage in solving various high computational complexity problems arising in signal processing and optimizations of various tasks of 6G and beyond. Even though the great potential, the blend between quantum information technologies and 6G encounters many challenges from both academia and industry. It is recommended that more attentions and efforts need to be invested. Particularly, the cross-domain cooperations, such as cooperations from the communication and physics, and from the academia and industry, are of great significance for facilitating the fusion. Moreover, finding typical use cases that blend both quantum information technology and 6G are vital at this initial development stage. This WWRF white paper offers many most important aspects of quantum information technology for 6G, which serves as a benchmark for supporting continuous future research.

4. List of Figures

Figure 1-1 The envisioned usage scenarios and capabilities of 6G (ITU, 2023).	5
Figure 2-1 The typical three-stage quantum sensing principle (Kitching et al, 2011)...	12
Figure 2-2 The RAQR-aided wireless reception scheme (Gong & Sun et al, 2024). ...	15
Figure 2-3 Quantum computing applications in 6G and beyond.	20

5. List of Tables

Table 1-1 Quantum information technologies with 6G KPIs.....	8
Table 2-1 Challenges of quantum communications for 6G and beyond.....	11
Table 2-2 Representative technologies for realizing quantum sensing	13
Table 2-3 Quantum sensing application in 6G and beyond.....	14
Table 2-4 Representative technologies for realizing quantum computing	19
Table 2-5 Representative algorithms for realizing quantum computing	21

6. References

- ITU Recommendation (2023). Framework and overall objectives of the future development of IMT for 2030 and beyond. International Telecommunication Union (ITU) Recommendation (ITU-R).
- Dowling, J. P., & Milburn, G. J. (2003). Quantum technology: the second quantum revolution. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 361(1809), 1655-1674.
- Pirandola, S., Andersen, U. L., Banchi, L., Berta, M., Bunandar, D., Colbeck, R., ... & Wallden, P. (2020). Advances in quantum cryptography. *Advances in optics and photonics*, 12(4), 1012-1236.
- Mao, Y., Wang, B. X., Zhao, C., Wang, G., Wang, R., Wang, H., ... & Pan, J. W. (2018). Integrating quantum key distribution with classical communications in backbone fiber network. *Optics express*, 26(5), 6010-6020.
- Mehic, M., Michalek, L., Dervisevic, E., Burdiak, P., Plakalovic, M., Rozhon, J., ... & Voznak, M. (2023). Quantum cryptography in 5G networks: a comprehensive overview. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*.
- Chiti, F., Picchi, R., & Pierucci, L. (2022). Metropolitan quantum-drone networking and computing: A software-defined perspective. *IEEE Access*, 10, 126062-126073.
- Chen, Y., Wang, Y., Wang, Z., & Zhang, P. (2024). Holographic Multiple-Input, Multiple-Output Systems: Their Channel Estimation and Performance. *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*.
- Gong, T., Gavriilidis, P., Ji, R., Huang, C., Alexandropoulos, G. C., Wei, L., ... & Yuen, C. (2023). Holographic MIMO communications: Theoretical foundations, enabling technologies, and future directions. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*.
- Yin, J., Cao, Y., Li, Y. H., Liao, S. K., Zhang, L., Ren, J. G., ... & Pan, J. W. (2017). Satellite-based entanglement distribution over 1200 kilometers. *Science*, 356(6343), 1140-1144.
- Prateek, K., Ojha, N. K., Altaf, F., & Maity, S. (2023). Quantum secured 6G technology-based applications in Internet of Everything. *Telecommunication Systems*, 82(2), 315-344.
- Kim, M., Kasi, S., Lott, P. A., Venturelli, D., Kaewell, J., & Jamieson, K. (2021). Heuristic quantum optimization for 6G wireless communications. *IEEE Network*, 35(4), 8-15.
- Azuma, K., Economou, S. E., Elkouss, D., Hilaire, P., Jiang, L., Lo, H. K., & Tzitrin, I. (2023). Quantum repeaters: From quantum networks to the quantum internet. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 95(4), 045006.
- Sangouard, N., Simon, C., De Riedmatten, H., & Gisin, N. (2011). Quantum repeaters based on atomic ensembles and linear optics. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 83(1), 33-80.
- Van Meter, R., & Touch, J. (2013). Designing quantum repeater networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 51(8), 64-71.
- Deepanramkumar, P., & Helensharmila, A. (2024). AI-Enhanced Quantum-Secured IoT Communication Framework for 6G Cognitive Radio Networks. *IEEE Access*.
- Fernández-Caramés, T. M. (2019). From pre-quantum to post-quantum IoT security: A survey on quantum-resistant cryptosystems for the Internet of Things. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(7), 6457-6480.
- Fowler, A. G., Mariantoni, M., Martinis, J. M., & Cleland, A. N. (2012). Surface codes: Towards practical large-scale quantum computation. *Physical Review A—Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics*, 86(3), 032324.

-
- Liu, Y., Zhao, Q., Li, M. H., Guan, J. Y., Zhang, Y., Bai, B., ... & Pan, J. W. (2018). Device-independent quantum random-number generation. *Nature*, 562(7728), 548-551.
- Taneja, A., & Rani, S. (2024). Quantum-Enabled Intelligent Resource Control for Reliable Communication Support in Internet-of-Vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics*.
- Wang, C., & Rahman, A. (2022). Quantum-enabled 6G wireless networks: Opportunities and challenges. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 29(1), 58-69.
- Kitching, J., Knappe, S., & Donley, E. A. (2011). Atomic sensors—a review. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 11(9), 1749-1758.
- Gong, T., Chandra, A., Yuen, C., Guan, Y. L., Dumke, R., See, C. M. S., ... & Hanzo, L. (2024). Rydberg Atomic Quantum Receivers for Classical Wireless Communication and Sensing. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.14501*.
- Meyer, D. H., Cox, K. C., Fatemi, F. K., & Kunz, P. D. (2018). Digital communication with Rydberg atoms and amplitude-modulated microwave fields. *Applied Physics Letters*, 112(21).
- Cai, Y., Shi, S., Zhou, Y., Li, Y., Yu, J., Li, W., & Li, L. (2023). High-sensitivity Rydberg-atom-based phase-modulation receiver for frequency-division-multiplexing communication. *Physical Review Applied*, 19(4), 044079.
- Yuan, J., Jin, T., Xiao, L., Jia, S., & Wang, L. (2023). A Rydberg atom-based receiver with amplitude modulation technique for the fifth-generation millimeter-wave wireless communication. *IEEE antennas and wireless propagation letters*.
- Zhang, P., Yuan, S., Jing, M., Yuan, J., Zhang, H., & Zhang, L. (2024). Image Transmission Utilizing Amplitude Modulation in Rydberg Atomic Antenna. *IEEE Photonics Journal*.
- Gong, T., Sun, J., Yuen, C., Hu, G., Zhao, Y., Guan, Y. L., ... & Hanzo, L. (2024). Rydberg Atomic Quantum Receivers for Classical Wireless Communications and Sensing: Their Models and Performance. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.05554*.
- Gong, T., Yuen, C., See, C. M. S., Debbah, M. & Hanzo, L. (2024). Rydberg atomic quantum receivers for the multi-user MIMO uplink. *arXiv*.
- Gong, T., Yuen, C., C., See, C. M. S., Debbah, M. & Hanzo, L. (2024). Rydberg atomic quantum receivers for DOA estimation. *arXiv*.
- Wade, C. G., Šibalić, N., De Melo, N. R., Kondo, J. M., Adams, C. S., & Weatherill, K. J. (2017). Real-time near-field terahertz imaging with atomic optical fluorescence. *Nature Photonics*, 11(1), 40-43.
- Arumugam, D., Park, J. H., Feyissa, B., Bush, J., & Mysore Nagaraja, S. P. (2024). Remote sensing of soil moisture using Rydberg atoms and satellite signals of opportunity. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 18025.
- Holloway, C. L., Gordon, J. A., Jefferts, S., Schwarzkopf, A., Anderson, D. A., Miller, S. A., ... & Raithel, G. (2014). Broadband Rydberg atom-based electric-field probe for SI-traceable, self-calibrated measurements. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 62(12), 6169-6182.
- Lloyd, S. (2008). Enhanced sensitivity of photodetection via quantum illumination. *Science*, 321(5895), 1463-1465.
- Luong, D., Balaji, B., & Rajan, S. (2023). Quantum radar: Challenges and outlook: An overview of the state of the art. *IEEE Microwave Magazine*, 24(9), 61-67.
- Botsinis, P., Alanis, D., Babar, Z., Nguyen, H. V., Chandra, D., Ng, S. X., & Hanzo, L. (2018). Quantum search algorithms for wireless communications. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 21(2), 1209-1242.
- Qu, Z., Chen, Z., Ning, X., & Tiwari, P. (2023). QEPP: A quantum efficient privacy protection protocol in 6G-quantum internet of vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*.
-

- Mastroianni, C., Plastina, F., Settino, J., & Vinci, A. (2024). Variational Quantum Algorithms for the Allocation of Resources in a Cloud/Edge Architecture. *IEEE Transactions on Quantum Engineering*.
- Zaman, F., Farooq, A., Ullah, M. A., Jung, H., Shin, H., & Win, M. Z. (2023). Quantum machine intelligence for 6G URLLC. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 30(2), 22-30.
- Tariq, S., Arfeto, B. E., Khalid, U., Kim, S., Duong, T. Q., & Shin, H. (2024). Deep Quantum-Transformer Networks for Multi-Modal Beam Prediction in ISAC Systems. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*.
- Kasi, S., Sud, J., Jamieson, K., & Ravi, G. S. (2024). A Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm-based Decoder Architecture for NextG Wireless Channel Codes. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.11726*.

7. List of Abbreviations

5G	Fifth-Generation
6G	Sixth-Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Direction of Arrival
DARPA	Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency
EM	Electromagnetic
ESA	European Space Agency
FEC	Forward Error Correction
GEO	GEostationary Orbit
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HHL	Harrow Hassidim Lloyd
IoE	Internet of Everything
IoT	Internet of Things
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDPC	Low Density Parity Check
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LLM	Large Language Model
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NISQ	Noisy Intermediate Scale Quantum
PQC	Post Quantum Cryptography
QAOA	Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm
QEC	Quantum Error Correction
QeMS	Quantum-Enabled Meta-Surfaces
QFT	Quantum Fourier Transform
QIA	Quantum Internet Alliance
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
QNN	Quantum Neural Networks
QoS	Quality of Service
QoE	Quality of Experience
QRNG	Quantum Random Number Generation
QTMS	Quantum Two-Mode Squeezing
QTN	Quantum Transformer Networks
RAQS	Rydberg atomic quantum sensor

RAQR	Rydberg atomic quantum receiver
SNR	Signal-to-Noise-Ratio
SWaP-C	Size, Weight, Power, and Cost
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable & Low-Latency Communication
VQE	Variational Quantum Eigensolver
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
WWRF	Wireless World Research Forum

Imprint

Wireless World Research Forum
c/o Format A AG
Wiesenstraße 9
CH-8034 Zürich

Secretariat:
Vinod Kumar
e-Mail: vinod.kumar@wwrf.ch
Phone and Fax : +33611181622

The WWRF is a non-profit organisation registered in Switzerland.

Chairman of the Forum:
Dr. Nigel Jefferies

Editor-in-Chief: Dr. Nigel Jefferies

The WWRF **Outlook** Visions and research directions for the Wireless World
ISSN 1662-615X is published non-periodically by the Wireless World Research Forum
<http://www.wwrf.ch>

Responsibility for the contents rests with the Steering Board of the Forum.